
Deliverable: Transmission pathways of *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC, and antimicrobial resistance from animals, food, and environment to humans: One-Health characterisation of the source and components and options to inform control policies.

Final conclusions and recommendations for the use of source attribution approach into One-health framework for surveillance and control of *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC, and antimicrobial resistance

D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.2 - D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.2

Workpackage 5

Responsible Partner: ISS

Contributing partners: DTU, ANSES, APHA, BfR, DAFM, INIAV, INSA, ISS, NIPH, NVI, PHE, PIWET, RIVM, SSI, SVA, Teagasc, UU-NCOH, VRI, WBVR, VISAVET

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRPFZ-1-WP5.1		
Project Acronym	DiSCoVeR		
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Due month of the report	57		
Actual submission month	60		
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.;</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R Save date: 19/12/2022		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Preamble - Rationale

The source attribution (SA) exercise carried out by the DiSCoVeR project aimed at evaluating through different methodological approaches how much different animal reservoirs, food production chains and transmission routes contribute to the burden of disease in humans caused by *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, Shigatoxin-producing *E.coli* (STEC) and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) with particular focus on Extended-Spectrum Beta-lactamase *E. coli*.

SA has been defined as the partitioning of a human disease burden to specific animal sources (Pires et al. 2009). However, the application of SA studies to animals and to livestock may be sub-optimal for zoonotic foodborne pathogens because of their complex epidemiology involving their common spread to humans also by non-foodborne transmission routes, such as direct animal contact, through contaminated environmental sources (drinking water, wastewater, soil, top-soil improvers etc.), from non-food producing animal reservoirs (wildlife, pets including horses, etc.), or by human-to-human transmission. This is the case for all the hazards targeted by the DiSCoVeR, which are considered top-priority zoonotic foodborne hazards in the EU, but are well-known not to be 100% foodborne pathogens, but can be transmitted to humans from multiple reservoirs and transmission routes, going beyond the foodborne route.

SA is important to guide intervention to control the spread of zoonotic pathogens from and between animal reservoirs and non-human sources to humans and support decision making.

Which are the main results of the DiSCoVeR project?

The DiSCoVeR project adopted in a very practical way the One Health concept by bringing together and analysing jointly data from surveillance and monitoring of top-priority foodborne pathogens from different sectors (animal, food, feed, environment), as well as other data with the aim to produce scientific evidence to protect public and animal health. Data, metadata and other indicators on *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, STEC and ESBL *E.coli* in different sources and at different level of the transmission routes have been combined with data and metadata from human populations including specific high-risk subgroups (e.g. HUS subgroup for STEC), and through different methodological approaches evidence to support decision making has been produced. As such, the DiSCoVeR SA exercise and results may contribute with a One Health perspective to:

- support interventions and inform control programs in the different sectors including the evaluation of existing control efforts
- define the objectives and scopes of surveillance and monitoring programs for each foodborne pathogens, AMR at the EU and country level
- plan additional sampling and data collection in the different countries and sectors to fill existing data gaps
- optimise the metadata collection in the different sectors
- disclose new components (sources, reservoirs, and transmission routes) of the epi-cycle raising questions for further research

The DiSCoVeR results and community represent a proof of concept for SA for foodborne pathogens

Under the umbrella of the DiSCoVeR project, expertise and skills from multiple sectors and disciplines have been brought together into a small scientific One-Health community. Collaboration, integration, networking, as well as exchange of knowledge and skills among partners' experts (19 partners from 13 countries) allowed the experts to comprehensively approach 'SA science', including its main components (methods, data, knowledge, operational framework). This was an added value of the DiSCoVeR and an important achievement for future translation of the capacity building into the EU context. In this

perspective, DiSCoVeR results also go beyond the production of SA estimates and can be summarised as follows:

- Established framework for data collection, data evaluation and data sharing among partners complying with rules for open data (WP1)
- Collected and evaluated existing data for *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, STEC and ESBL isolate (WP2)
- Prepared datasets with typing/subtyping/sequence-based information and metadata available and made this data and dataset publicly accessible (WP2)
- Mapped knowledge and data gaps (WP)
- Reviewed, assessed and developed SA estimation methods with the aim to make models publicly accessible (WP3)
- Completed and compared the outcomes of numerous SA studies using different methodologies and according with the fit-for-purpose of data (WP4)
- Discussed SA results, potential bias affecting results and uncertainty (WP4+ all partners)
- Discussed SA results with main OHEJP stakeholders, how to improve both data and methodologies, how to support translation into the EU context and how to improve capacity building (WP5+ all partners)
- Mapped existing control programs for *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, STEC and ESBL in Europe in order to identify gaps in an One Health context (WP5)
- Delivered recommendations for future translation of outcomes in the EU context (WP5+ all partners)

Since these results have been thoroughly described in the DiSCoVeR deliverables, the present document focuses only on the main remarks, conclusions and recommendations that would facilitate the appraisal and use of the SA outcomes for decision-making process in surveillance and control of *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, STEC and ESBL, and the future research needs.

Making use of the DiSCoVeR source attribution results at the European level.

The epidemiological perspective: what the DiSCoVeR SA exercise tells us

What was 'already known':

Evidence coming from the DiSCoVeR confirmed what was well-known:

- Studies based on microbial typing/subtyping showed that *Salmonella* was linked to the largest variety of sources, but that pigs (and pork), laying hens (and eggs) and broilers chicken accounted for most cases followed by other livestock and non-food producing animals (pets) and environmental sources. Converging evidence from multiple SA methods showed that:
 - *Layers/eggs* were the main reservoir/source of human *S. Enteritidis* infections
 - *Pigs/pork* were the main reservoir/source of human *S. Typhimurium* infections including its monophasic variant
 - *Broiler chickens* were the main reservoir/source of human *S. Infantis* infections
 - Human *S. Derby* infections were mainly acquired from pigs/pork and cattle/beef

Other studies highlighted the importance of non-foodborne transmission routes for *Salmonella*, in particular contact with animals (including pets), water consumption, occupational exposures and environmental sources (including water).

- All studies on *Campylobacter* based on microbial subtyping confirmed broilers (chicken meat) as the most important source. Also, *Campylobacter* outcomes resulting from other approaches

contributed to define the importance of risk factors and non-foodborne transmission routes, in particular contact with animals (including pets), behavioural and environmental exposures.

- Results from studies based on microbial typing/subtyping for STEC showed that human cases were mainly attributable to the cattle reservoir, in particular for children, followed by other domestic (sheep and goats) and wild ruminants (deer, reindeers).

It is important to underline that the DiSCoVeR results strengthen the already available evidence about well-established sources in several ways:

- The DiSCoVeR differs from previous SA studies in Europe, as it was aimed to frame the SA exercise under a wider One-Health conceptual perspective embracing humans, livestock, pets, wildlife, environmental sources and considering, where possible, directionality of transmission routes.
- SA was applied in DiSCoVeR using multiple methodological approaches in parallel, sometimes also using the same input data to i) maximise the exploitation of the existing data (i.e. DiSCoVeR partners' data as well as publicly available data) ii) encompass the main focal levels of the epidemiological transmission pathways (i.e. the reservoir level and the exposure level), and iii) better characterise sources and transmission routes through the combination of outcomes from different approaches. This integrative approach allowed putting emphasis on the significance of converging evidence (i.e. similar SA outcomes obtained from the application of different methods) and, conversely, conflicting outcomes contributed to evaluate the quality of the data, the appropriateness of the methods, the accuracy of the estimates, and the uncertainty around specific outcomes.
- The application of SA methods making use of WGS data (machine-learning, population structure) allowed to remarkably reduce the uncertainty compared to previous studies since the use of sequence-based characterisation methods have a high discriminatory power.
- Although past experiences were reported for SA sequence-based studies, the DiSCoVeR allowed to conduct SA at a large-scale at the European-level (WP4) thanks to the availability of large high-quality (fit for purpose) datasets. This is an important achievement of the DiSCoVeR and of the OHEJP consortium in terms of outcomes and uncertainty that have been made available to end-users of scientific evidence, i.e. primarily public health authorities, other stakeholders including farmers, industry etc.) to be taken into account for future development of policy of intervention to protect public and animal health and support sustainability of primary production.
- Although the role of cattle (and bovine meat) and ruminants for STEC was well known, mainly due to outbreaks reporting, very few SA studies had been conducted previously.

What's 'new'

For foodborne pathogens, unexpected or less frequently reported findings emerged from the DiSCoVeR SA analyses, in particular on the role of 'horses and donkeys' for *S. Enteritidis*, 'reptiles' for *S. Newport*, 'pigs' and 'wild-boars' for STEC in specific countries. These findings represent interesting clues to extend the focus of surveillance and research activities in the future, although caution is recommended for the following reasons:

- Data on these sources were scarce in the DiSCoVeR dataset and in many cases they referred to sources not usually included in surveillance or explored in SA.
- The uncertainty around the resulting attribution estimates were high, due to the paucity of data and the lack of a clear sampling framework resulting in less representative data.
- Interpretation of these results would need a better characterisation of exposure pattern in particular of the directionality of transmission routes linking humans, animals and the

environment. In particular, the interpretation of ‘horses and donkeys’ as potential sources for *S. Enteritidis* needs to consider the directionality of potential transmission, as ‘reverse causality’ may play a role. Indeed, foals in particular often get symptomatic salmonellosis (as also humans do), and the isolates from horses and donkeys used in the analyses originate from sick animals; thus, it might be that humans contribute to infect these animals or that both humans and equids have common/shared sources of infection from which they both get infected in parallel.

Potential bias linked to DiSCoVeR results

SA is a data-driven exercise. Attribution results depend on the type and quality of data feeding the models, which raises some important remarks:

- Inclusion of data on isolates with no information on the reason for sampling and poor metadata may introduce bias. The selection of accurate and representative data from multiple sources/reservoirs is crucial, and selecting isolates coming from ‘random sampling’ would be best practice for SA.
- Increasing sample sizes from less frequently explored sources resulting in higher genetic diversity of the investigated pathogens may lead to higher attribution estimates in those sources, simply because the probability of finding near matches with isolates from humans increases. In DiSCoVeR, a clear example of this was evident for the attribution estimates for *Campylobacter* in the Netherlands, where abundant data from several other sources than broilers were available.
- Unbalanced datasets characterised by oversampling of a few sources (e.g. *Salmonella* in poultry) and data sparsity and paucity for other sources, is likely going to result in some degree of estimates biased towards the best investigated sources. This was particularly evident for environmental sources that were underrepresented in almost all DiSCoVeR datasets compared to livestock particularly those animal species targeted by control programs and/or baseline surveys.

How the DiSCoVeR results could provide information to improve data collection within surveillance and monitoring programs in humans and non-human sources

Results of the DiSCoVeR and in particular analysis of the knowledge gap and SA estimates may contribute to:

- Identify sources needing better coverage in terms of sampling and information on the sampling context.
- Suggest optimal sampling approach and isolate selection criteria for the purpose of SA.
- Suggest optimal and minimum data reporting requirements as regard of characterisation of the agents, and according with the SA methods applied. SA models based on highly discriminatory characterisation methods allow for more accurate SA estimation, but also often lead many human cases unresolved. In addition, WGS-based data may be scarce for multiple sources, while data obtained with pheno/genotyping methods (e.g. *Salmonella* serovars, STEC O group, *stx* type) are easier to obtain within national and EU surveillance and monitoring plans.
- Highlight the need for harmonisation of surveillance and monitoring data collection across human and non-human sectors.
- Improve capacity-building within surveillance, disease burden estimation, and source attribution estimation.

How the DiSCoVeR results could inform control policies

Outcomes of the SA exercise are of particular relevance to answer scientific questions posed by risk managers in order to protect public and animal health. Evidence emerging from SA can thoroughly inform

the decision-making process for the establishment of control strategies to mitigate the risk posed by foodborne zoonotic agents to humans:

- The DiSCoVeR SA provides evidence of the reservoirs most implicated in the transmission of foodborne infections to humans, routes of transmission, and possible risk factors also in relation to high vulnerable population sub-groups.
- Quantitative SA studies providing accurate estimates and characterisation of the uncertainty around the estimates.
- SA can be used to assess the effectiveness of existing control programs through studies aiming to evaluate, if the importance of reservoirs targeted by the interventions have changed before and afterward, i.e. if the number of human cases attributed to specific sources have declined following the application of specific intervention strategies in the reservoir.

Matching evidence from DiSCoVeR and existing control programs

Existing control programs and intervention strategies for *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, STEC AMR in European countries have been mapped under the DiSCoVeR, to provide insight where intervention would be necessary.

- ***Salmonella*** was the agent most frequently target by control programs in the European countries, mainly due to the implementation of National Control Programs (NCP) at the EU level in poultry population (Reg. (EC) 2160/2003) for certain serovars and microbiological food safety and hygiene criteria within the food production chain (Reg. (EC) 2073/2005 and Reg. (EU) No 2019/627). No NCP in pigs coordinated at the EU level exist, although pigs and pork were the most implicated sources identified by the DiSCoVeR for many *Salmonella* serovars. Mapping results showed that less than half European countries implemented control programs and/or intervention strategies at national level (9 countries based on literature review; 7/21 according to experts survey).
- Microbiological process hygiene criteria are also available for ***Campylobacter*** in broilers at slaughter in accordance with Reg. (EC) No. 2073/2005 and Reg. No 2019/627. No NCP exist in broilers at primary level coordinated at the EU level. Control programs/actions at country level was reported in broilers for a few countries (N=5) in the structured literature report and in a higher proportion of countries in the expert survey (10/13).
- Microbiological criteria for **STEC** top-6 serogroups in sprouts are only available at the EU level. At the country level, control programs/actions were mapped through the experts' survey for 7/9 and 5/9 in beef and dairy cattle, respectively.

Inputs from the stakeholders

Achievements of the DiSCoVeR project were discussed during the final stakeholder on-line meeting held on 18/11/2022. Representatives from the EU Commission (DG SANTE), institutional OH-EJP partners (EFSA and ECDC), EU reference laboratories (EURL) for *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *E.coli* and AMR, and DiSCoVeR partners were attending the meeting. Main inputs received from stakeholders with regard of the use and communication of SA evidence, translation of the DiSCoVeR approach and capacity-building into the EU context were discussed as reported below:

- **Use of DiSCoVeR SA evidence:**
 - Use of evidence from SA DiSCoVeR including new elements, will be considered for future reflections at the EU level. However, adaptation of the current legal framework for zoonoses monitoring and control in EU requires time and implies proportionality and subsidiarity, also for Member States. The process should involve EFSA and EU member states as end-user of evidence and should be based on 'recommendations'. Decisions are taken based on the evaluation of scientific evidence, but also other elements,

particularly cost-benefit analysis, meaning that the advantage of taking actions (i.e. reduced human disease burden and potential competitive advantage for food producers) should exceed the administrative and financial burden. Such an evaluation was conducted several years ago for *Salmonella* in pigs and pork following the EU-wide baseline study. The conclusions of the evaluation did not in favour taking actions meaning that EU-coordinated surveillance and control programs as implemented in the poultry sector is not existing for pigs and/or pork even though this reservoir is the most important source of human salmonellosis in many member states. Under the current legal framework, however, evidence can be used by single MS, if they so choose.

- Comprehensive understanding of possible reasons underlying non-expected SA results need to be explored carefully.
- **Translation in the EU context:**
 - **Data and dataset**
 - Synergies with other existing harmonised baselines studies could be explored to obtain isolates (upon voluntary testing by MS) from sources underrepresented and enlarge datasets underpinning SA.
 - The possibility to take actions in specific possible reservoirs such as environment and wildlife should be considered when new sampling is to be implemented since this is a resource consuming activity.
 - The collected DiSCoVeR WGS datasets are a big achievement and sharing them would be very important, also for other purposes than source attribution (e.g. pan-genome analysis, risk assessments). A possibility is represented by EFSA and ECDC databases for animal food and human genomic sequences, respectively or other publicly accessible databases such as ENA.
 - **Technical capacity**
 - Sequence-based data is not considered a problem for EURL-NRLs networks. There is generally a good capacity in all networks to produce genomic data, although analysis of the genomic data to 'prepare' them SA requires bioinformatics expertise.
 - **Best practice**
 - The DiSCoVeR project was considered an example of good 'One-Health practice'. Cross-sectoral collaboration worked very well, skills, trust and data sharing were key for completing the SA studies, which were done in collaboration across partner institutes with minimal 'silo' work.
- **Fields of recommended short-term future application:**
 - ESBL in *Salmonella*, in particular the directionality of exposure to explore the possible intra-specific transmission in humans and animals, and origin of specific ESBL clones
 - Yersinia infections are on the rise in many countries, and although pigs are a well-known reservoir for this pathogen and human disease often linked to consumption of uncooked pork, attribution analyses could be useful to confirm that this association is still valid and to explore possible other sources and risk factors.
 - Attribution of AMR and the role of the environment for the dissemination of resistance genes is getting much attention, as evidence is needed for targeted surveillance and control at the EU level.

Conclusions

Based on the work and deliverables from WP1-4, the DiSCoVeR partners discussed and agreed on the following overall conclusions for the DiSCoVeR project:

- Quantifying the role of the environment, wildlife and pets as sources for human infections remains a challenge complicated by bi/multi-directional transmission and data scarcity. Some planned studies addressing these sources and reservoirs were cancelled or delayed due to COVID, whereas those performed in general only contributed with few data point making interpretation difficult.
- Despite this uncertainty, our findings clearly identify livestock populations as the main reservoirs for all target pathogens except for ESBL, where human-to-human transmission are more important. From a risk assessment point of view, particularly, *Salmonella* in pigs and pork and *Campylobacter* in broilers and chicken meat stand out as areas, where targeted future control and intervention could be implemented to reduce the burden of human infections significantly.
- Despite the observed discrepancies between model results, most can be explained, and the majority points in the same directions given credibility to both the results and the model approaches.
- Application of WGS-based data for attribution holds some clear advantages with regard to model specificity, but they are resource demanding requiring more technical expertise, time and computer capacity, and phenotypic and/or epidemiological models may in some instances give results that are just as useful for the risk managers.
- Using metagenomics for AMR attribution is a very promising approach to an otherwise wicked challenge. However, it need to be explored how it works on resistomes obtained from the general population, which were unfortunately not available for the project.
- A collection of standardised datasets from several countries and time periods provides more robust results and makes it possible to observe trends that are otherwise difficult to see including effects of control and prevention efforts.

Final recommendations in a OH frame

The line of thinking behind One Health is by no means a new concept (Evans and Leighton, 2014). In fact, it can be traced as far back as to the time of Aristotle, and the concept has during the last decade been defined by different organisations in slightly varied versions (see text box below). Recently, the major players i.e., the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE), the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the World Health Organization (WHO) agreed to a new operational definition of One Health proposed by their advisory panel consisting of members representing a broad range of disciplines in science and policy-related sectors. This new One Health definition states: “One Health is an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimize the **health of people, animals and ecosystems**. It recognizes the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and the wider environment (including ecosystems) are closely linked and inter-dependent. The approach mobilizes **multiple sectors, disciplines and communities** at varying levels of society to work together to foster well-being and tackle threats to health and ecosystems, while addressing the collective need for clean water, energy and air, safe and nutritious food, taking action on climate change, and **contributing to sustainable development**”. Importantly, “animals” include both domesticated species and wildlife, and the previously used term “environment” is now changed to ecosystem health, which also addresses biodiversity. One Health is, therefore, also to be concerned with the impact and consequences of anthropogenic activities such as climate change, deforestation, overharvesting and pollution.

DEFINITIONS OF ONE HEALTH

'One Health is the collaborative effort of multiple health science professions, together with their related disciplines and institutions – working locally, nationally, and globally – to attain optimal health for people, domestic animals, wildlife, plants, and our environment.'
One Health Commission

'A collaborative, international, cross-sectoral, multidisciplinary mechanism to address threats and reduce risks of detrimental infectious diseases at the animal-human-ecosystem interface.'
Food and Agriculture Organization

The **World Organisation for Animal Health**, while not specifically defining One Health, endorses the approach as 'a collaborative and all-encompassing way to address, when relevant, animal and public health globally. This collaboration should not be limited to only the international level, but must be translated as a new and fundamental paradigm at national levels'.

'One Health' is an integrated, unifying approach to balance and optimize the health of people, animals and the environment. The approach mobilizes multiple sectors, disciplines and communities at varying levels of society to work together. This way, new and better ideas are developed that address root causes and create long-term, sustainable solutions.
The World Health Organisation

The **One Health Initiative** considers One Health to be 'a worldwide strategy for expanding interdisciplinary collaborations and communications in all aspects of health care for humans, animals, and the environment'.

The **One Health Global Network** considers that the aim of One Health is to 'improve health and wellbeing through the prevention of risks and the mitigation of effects of crises that originate at the interface between humans, animals and their various environments'.

The **One Health Committee of the World Small Animal Veterinary Association** comments that 'One Health or One Medicine proposes the unification of the medical and veterinary professions with the establishment of collaborative ventures in clinical care, surveillance and control of cross-species disease, education, and research into disease pathogenesis, diagnosis, therapy and vaccination. The concept encompasses the human population, domestic animals and wildlife and the impact that environmental changes ('environmental health') such as global warming will have on these populations.'

*Adapted from
Gibbs (2014) | Veterinary Record | 85*

Despite the clear definition and presumably good intentions, there seems still to be an unbalanced focus on human health and health of livestock i.e., animals with a clear economic value, when it comes to One Health initiatives within foodborne diseases. Obviously human health and livestock have a very central role for foodborne diseases, as we could also conclude from our gap analysis, where we found that the vast majority of surveillance and control activities are still within these domains with very few activities in other areas e.g., wildlife, urban synantropic animal populations, and the environment. However, as we have also shown, wildlife does play a role in disease transmission and sustainment of disease as reservoirs, even if they do not directly comprise a major source of human infections. In addition, and because most samples are from livestock and animal-derived food, the estimated importance of e.g., cattle as a reservoir for *Campylobacter* and STEC may to some extent reflect a proxy for some environmental contamination that is not directly monitored. For instance, we did find that when otherwise not well-monitored sources were included in the models (e.g., solipeds, wild ruminants, wild boars, fruit and vegetable, and reptiles), their relative importance as a source for human infections tended to depend on the number of included samples. This was especially observed for the subtyping source attribution approaches, where a larger number of isolates/sequences generally resulted in more subtype diversity within a source, thereby increasing the probability of matches with subtypes found in humans. The observed results are therefore to some extent biased by the number of isolates available.

To address some of these issues and fill identified data and surveillance gaps, a strengthening of the One Health reporting of foodborne disease and zoonoses could be considered by increasing the focus on selected environmental reservoirs, as well as non-animal foods such as fruit and vegetables. However, traditional sampling of these sources for foodborne pathogens may not be very cost-effective. Several studies including some that are part of DiSCoVeR have collected hundreds of samples with few positive findings. Hence, development and application of "smarter" approaches are needed, for instance monitoring of relevant indicators, like the quality of drinking water is monitored for faecal contamination and not specific pathogens. Making use of infrastructure from other national or EU monitoring programs not related to food safety could also be an option to increase efficiency and potentially optimise resources.

We, therefore, propose to **increase transdisciplinary research collaboration**, including e.g. experts working with wildlife conservation and environmental protection both at national and EU level. A first step would be to identify possible areas of synergy including (existing) monitoring of indicators of wildlife

and environmental health that may also be of value for monitoring zoonoses and foodborne diseases. An example of a novel way of monitoring water, and fruit and vegetables could be metagenomics analyses looking for species-specific faecal contamination (Bernard et al., 2021). A call for public participation in data collection (e.g. dog owners submitting dog-poo collecting bags, hunters sampling game, etc.) could also be explored.

Further research studies to understand the transmission pathways including the **directionality of transmission** are also needed for most of the foodborne pathogens and in particular for *Campylobacter*, STEC, and AMR in pathogens and commensals. The fact that we do not know the baseline of environmental contamination makes it very hard to interpret the findings done in limited studies and put the results in context to food safety and human and animal health in general.

Improved One Health surveillance should be facilitated by **increased and easier data sharing** including an increased level of detail regarding the individual samples. As discovered in this project, the current minimum data required for member states (MS) to report are not sufficient for source attribution or any detailed analysis of trends. For example, many MS do not report serotyping or other subtyping information even, if the information exist.

Barriers for data sharing are many. Some are technical challenges associated with datasets becoming increasingly larger and more complex, but also several economic, legal, and political barriers make sharing health-related data difficult (Schwalbe et al., 2020). Ideally, all relevant data and information between human, food, animals, and environmental sectors should be shared. This may require a change in legislation making it mandatory to share certain types of data. Such additional data could also include results from the food industry's own check programmes. Obviously increased sharing of data and the level of data detail should be controlled by legislation and still be protective of both the individual and private entities by securing anonymity and circumvent apprehensions about confidentiality. However, anonymous data with a comprehensive set of specified metadata can still be of great value for surveillance and control.

Data owners also need to be assured that it is safe to share their data and there should be transparency about the use of the data. Policies for data sharing should be clearly formulated, so that concerns about inappropriate or out-of-context use of the data is circumvented to the extent possible. Data providers may also be worried about not receiving acknowledgement, or that others will use their data to gain scientific recognition.

Data sharing is also often hampered by lack of compatibility between databases and platforms. When many stakeholders from different sectors are to share data, the infrastructure need to accommodate easy sharing, preferably so that data only have to be reported in one place.

Shared **data should be FAIR** i.e., the data should meet the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (Wilkinson et al., 2016). As we discovered through our project, data that we could have made good use of were available, but not accessible either because the data owners did not have time to do the data extraction and anonymisation, or it would take too long to get the permissions to share the more raw data. The former reason lead to another important point about the **value of data sharing** – or put in another way: “what’s in it for me?” If those collecting and owning the data are not themselves in need of data from other sources, why should they use time and energy to share their data? This is a valid reason and may only be overcome by data-sharing policies requiring certain data to be shared.

The overall value of data sharing in the scientific community builds on the logic that data sharing encourages more connection and collaboration between researchers, which can result in important new findings within a field. Furthermore, it allows sharing of resources, which should increase efficiency of public funds invested in research, surveillance, and control. However, data sharing requires a great deal of effort, resources, and collaboration. Preparing data to be shared takes time and careful documentation. When data providers (e.g. diagnostic labs, microbiologists) and data users (e.g. epidemiologists, risk assessors) differs, the need for or prioritisation of data sharing may differ, thereby

impeding data sharing.

It is becoming increasingly more common that scientific journals require that data used in a publication is shared openly. This is definitely a major step in the right direction as it is putting focus on data sharing. However, much of the data shared in this way is not the raw data actually collected or used in the study, but rather processed/aggregated data shared in specific formats and not easily combined with other data sources for use in for instance new research studies. An exception to this is the public archives for sharing sequence data e.g., the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). Here raw sequence data are shared in a standardised format with a minimum set of metadata, and although the accompanying metadata not always have sufficient detail or the interpretation can be ambiguous, the principle of a common repository with standardised data is commendable and should be extended to other types of data relevant for One Health surveillance.

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